

Statement by Eurodoc & the MCAA: Wishlist for the ERA Act

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) and the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) welcome the upcoming European Research Act (ERA Act). In its 25 years of existence, the European Research Area (ERA) has contributed significantly to strengthening the region's competitiveness. However, there are still large discrepancies throughout the region. It is our hope that the ERA Act can help reduce these disparities and further increase the ERA's competitiveness.

1. Promote and protect scientific freedom

Scientific freedom needs protection **through EU legislation**. In addition, considering that scientific and academic freedom are values fundamental to democracy, upholding them should be an integral part of soft policy-making strategies. In light of the backsliding of democracy experienced across the world, strengthening trust in science and experts is key to ensure a common basis of knowledge and understanding. Particularly considering the risks of disinformation, a shared knowledge base, including science as a key reference point, is crucial for democratic cohesion.

The ERA Act must introduce the following concrete measure:

- **Enhance the professional protection of researchers** by establishing an ombudsperson for academic freedom for researchers at the European level to represent researchers in cases where their academic freedom may be threatened.

2. Ensure competitiveness and promote and protect open science

Amidst growing concerns about research security, it is important to remember that the result of research is knowledge, which must be openly shared to hold value for society. Rather than closing off, and in alignment with Europe's values and principles, we should invest in researchers' and innovators' abilities to uphold democratic values and conduct their research as **openly as possible** while navigating a complex world and changing geopolitical environment.

The ERA Act must introduce the following concrete measures:

- **Strengthen fair competition and promote competitiveness** by ensuring transparency about other sectors' contributions to research funding and involvement in research.
- **Strengthen the region's competitiveness as a whole**, by ensuring equitable opportunities across the Union and promoting initiatives that widen participation and strengthen the European Research Area.
- **Continue promoting research to be as open as possible and only as closed as necessary.**

3. Ensure responsible use of EU funds and enable European freedom

A mandatory standard needs to be introduced that requires all researchers, including doctoral candidates and postdocs, forming part of research projects financed through European Commission (EC) funds, to be employed. The release of any funding should be contingent on employment and access to standard social security. This also calls on the many Member States across Europe that still lack legislation for the employment of doctoral candidates to address this issue promptly.

Research has mobility, exchange, and collaboration at its core, which should be facilitated and not hindered by legislation and other frameworks. **Pursuing a research career in Europe can not come at the expense of social security.** The desire for increased international mobility and brain circulation within Europe runs against systemic barriers such as access to social security, exacerbated by the current nature of research careers with their short-term employment and the hurdles for obtaining (permanent) resident permits.

Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) should remain mandatory to access EU funds, a policy that has proven itself effective. The eligibility criterion needs to be completed by the introduction of compliance checks to

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ensure actual implementation of the GEPs.

The ERA Act must introduce the following concrete measure:

- **Use EC funds responsibly to promote competitiveness.** Gender equality plans should remain mandatory to access EC funds (European Research Council (ERC), Framework Programmes, Horizon Europe (HEU), etc.), and, similarly, access to EC funds should be contingent on researchers financed through these funds being employed and that their employment grants them full access to social security.

4. Increase the attractiveness of research careers and address mobility barriers

To ensure Europe's competitiveness now and in the future, research careers and careers in higher education must be made more attractive across Europe. This means delivering on the promise of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and ERA: **recognising the professional status of doctoral candidates as researchers by employing them and ensuring that they and other ECRs receive salaries and social rights comparable to their professional qualifications.**

Automatic recognition of academic degrees should be made a reality. Building on the Lisbon convention, the introduction of automatic recognition of academic degrees is the necessary next step to fulfilling the vision of brain circulation, mobility, exchange, and collaboration across Europe. Similarly important is the work towards the European degree.

The ERA Act must introduce the following concrete measures:

- **Ensure that research careers are attractive across the region** by recognising the professional and academic qualifications of doctoral candidates and Early Career Researchers (ECRs) and offering competitive salaries.
- **Ensure that all research workers hold EU-juridical worker status.** This includes transversal access to social security benefits, which would ensure a solid foundation for the promotion of the free movement of knowledge in the EU, including of researchers themselves and their families.
- **Ensure that all research professionals**, from R1 to R4 level, have transversal access to social security benefits. This would ensure a solid foundation for the promotion of the free movement of knowledge in the EU, including researchers themselves and their families.

5. Increase investments in R&I

Investments in civil Research and Innovation (R&I) are long-term investments. If the Framework Programme's (FP's) budget is absorbed into a future European Competitiveness Fund, the resources allocated to civil R&I will be subject to shifting political priorities, thereby threatening not only the freedom of science, but also Europe's future competitiveness.

The targets should be 3% of GDP for the combined public and private spending on R&I, and 1.25% of GDP for the public sector. The Commission has invited Member States to activate the national escape clause of the Stability and Growth Pact, which will provide them additional budgetary space to increase their defence spending. A similar measure could be taken to increase the R&I expenditure and to prompt reforms and investments by the Member States.

6. Ensuring independence and stability for the ERC and MSCA

To truly safeguard the future of European research, it's crucial to establish a permanent and robust structural framework for both the ERC and the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA). These programmes, recognised globally for their merit-based, bottom-up approach and their success in

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attracting and retaining top talent, are indispensable for maintaining Europe's scientific leadership. In a rapidly shifting geopolitical landscape, providing the ERC and MSCA with sufficient independence and **long-term stability**, including **dedicated funding**, infrastructure, and freedom from external interference, is vital. This **permanent autonomy** ensures that funding decisions remain solely driven by scientific excellence and researcher-defined agendas. Allowing these highly successful initiatives to consistently foster groundbreaking discoveries, nurture research careers and strengthen Europe's global competitiveness when unhindered scientific progress is more critical than ever.

About this statement

This statement was approved by the 2024/2025 board of Eurodoc on 21.07.2025.

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List of Authors

- Pil Maria Saugmann, [0000-0002-3548-0134](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15461882)
- Gian Maria Greco, [0000-0002-8714-6349](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15462203)
- Nicola Dengo, [0000-0003-2534-7265](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13919031)
- Tereza Simova, [0000-0002-1774-4335](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13944737)
- Hannah Schoch, [0000-0002-3987-4106](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13745914)
- Mostafa Moonir Shawrav, [0000-0001-8639-0393](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796000)

Suggested Reading

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- Key Recommendations by the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) on the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Programme (2023). Marie Curie Alumni Association. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7834120>

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Contact: Eurodoc Board board@eurodoc.net and the MCAA contact@mariecuriealumni.eu

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network of researchers who have benefited from or are benefiting from the Marie (Skłodowska) Curie Actions. The MCAA supports and contributes to the advancement of knowledge for a global, diverse, and informed society. The main focus of the MCAA is to promote career development, offer networking opportunities and contribute to shaping the research and innovation policy. Currently, the MCAA has over 22,000 members from 150+ countries, covering all different career stages from diverse research fields. The MCAA has 38 geographical Chapters and 11 thematic Working Groups.